

Tools for the identification of key immune-active NLR and NLR pairs using ortholog gene expression data

V. Velásquez-Zapata¹, G.P. Cañas¹, F. López-Hernández¹, M.Á. Latorre-González¹, L.E. Cano-Gallego¹, M.F. Martínez², A.J. Cortés³, P.H. Reyes-Herrera⁴

¹AGROSAVIA – CI La Selva, Rionegro, Antioquia, Colombia

²AGROSAVIA – CI Palmira, Palmira, Valle del Cauca, Colombia

³Facultad de Ciencias Agrarias – Departamento de Ciencias Forestales, Universidad Nacional de Colombia – Sede Medellín

⁴AGROSAVIA – CI Tibaitatá, Mosquera, Cundinamarca, Colombia

Abstract

Effector triggered immunity (ETI) is an essential plant-defense mechanism against pathogens. R genes are responsible of activating such immune response. Experimental evidence shows that R genes converge to a group of genes named NOD-like receptors (NLRs). They have central roles in ETI activation and their coevolution with pathogen effectors drive a big part of the resistance mechanisms in plants. NLR characterization is a research priority for understanding the genetic and molecular mechanisms of plant resistance. Understanding better NLR functioning is of outstanding importance in plant breeding to improve crop resistance to the most devastating pathogens. Despite of the large body of literature that has accumulated showing NLR architecture and evolution, researchers have not reached the required resolution to narrow down the hundreds of candidates for functional validation. We propose to study this family further and understand the regulation of NLR-mediated plant defense by developing bioinformatic methods that prioritize on candidate NLRs and help to identify different mechanistic patterns of NLR regulation. With the current knowledge in NLR biology that has been generated using different bioinformatic tools and molecular techniques, we hypothesize that expression data and motif mining contain useful information to infer and prioritize NLR and NLR pairs. We present the bioinformatic tools that can be used to predict NLRs, NLR pair proteins and integrate ortholog search and RNASeq data to rank candidates through the inference of expression patterns.

NLRs constitute a gene family responsible for plant resistance

Effector triggered immunity (ETI) is an essential plant-defense mechanism against pathogens. Once pattern-triggered immunity (PTI) is broken, ETI performs as a second layer of defense that induces programmed host cell death. Unlike PTI, which is a general immunity strategy that recognizes conserved pathogen molecules, ETI is pathogen-specific. In nature, this phenomenon diversified through a 'gene for gene' evolutionary model between pathogen- avirulence (Avr) genes and plant resistance (R) genes. R genes are specially interesting for research since they are the basis of plant resistance, therefore, they can be used as a biotechnological tool for breeding purposes (Chisholm et al. 2006; J. D. G. Jones and Dangl 2006; Monteiro and Nishimura 2018).

Experimental evidence shows that R genes converge to a group of genes named NOD-like receptors (NLRs), one of the largest plant gene families. The gene structure of this family consists of modules or domains that include a N-terminal domain, a conserved nucleotide-binding domain (NB-ARC) and a leucine-rich repeat domain (LRR). When the N-terminal domain is further analyzed it is possible to distinguish two groups, the Toll-like/interleukin 1 domain (TIR-type NLRs) or a different domain (non-TIR-type NLRs), such as the coiled-coil domain CC-type NLR (Jacob, Vernaldi, and Maekawa 2013; Monteiro and Nishimura 2018). It has been seen that TIR-type NLRs use EDS1 (enhanced disease susceptibility 1) to activate the downstream signaling pathway, and non-TIR-type NLRs require NDR1 (non-race-specific disease resistance 1), which could indicate differences in the evolution of the signaling mechanisms (Borrelli et al. 2018).

The activation mechanism of NLRs is regulated by the NB-ARC domain. In absence of a pathogen, the LRR domain stabilizes the off state while the NB-ARC domain is bound to ADP. In contrast, in presence of an effector, the LRR domain recognizes it, inducing a conformational change and consequently, activating the NB-ARC domain with ATP binding, and triggering a defense signaling cascade (Borrelli et al. 2018). In some cases, the NLR activation only requires one receptor, however, there are other mechanisms where genetically linked NLRs are required to fulfil the function. These are known as NLR pairs, and their functions are divided in a way that one of them is in charge of recognize the effector and the second initiates the defense signaling pathway (Baggs, Dagdas, and Krasileva 2017). From the evolutionary perspective this is advantageous, since the separation of functions allows differential evolutionary rates, which is required to effector recognition and functional activation. Besides this direct recognition mechanism, there are more hypotheses that try to explain different indirect patterns of NLR activation. The first one is called the "guard" and the second the "decoy" hypothesis. In these models, the activation can occur indirectly through a helper protein, which can be the virulence target ("guard model") or a structural mimic of such a target ("decoy model") (Borrelli et al. 2018; Wu et al. 2017; Cesari et al. 2014; Monteiro and Nishimura 2018; Qi and Innes 2013).

As a first characterization approach of NLRs, multiple genome-wide comparative analyses of different plant species have been proposed (Yue et al. 2012; Chisholm et al. 2006; Steuernagel et al. 2015; Yang et al. 2008; Jupe et al. 2012; Kohler et al. 2008; Ameline-Torregrosa et al. 2007; Kang et al. 2012; Wan et al. 2013; Porter et al. 2009; Mun et al. 2009; J. Li et al. 2010; Guo et al. 2011; Meyers et al. 2003; Jacob, Vernaldi, and Maekawa 2013; Sarris et al. 2016). These comprise different bioinformatic methodologies that have revealed a major example of gene expansion and diversification. The main findings of those studies propose recombination, gene conversion, duplication, and selection as drivers for the evolution of NLRs, having a differential role depending of the species (Borrelli et al. 2018). Such sophisticated synergy of mechanisms for the maintenance of this genetic reservoir indicates their important role in plant immunity, and at the same time imposes a great challenge in the selection of candidates for functional validation.

In order to study this family further, and to understand the regulation of NLR-mediated plant defense, it is important to propose bioinformatic methods that prioritize on candidate NLRs and help to identify different mechanistic patterns of NLR regulation. From the functional perspective, those patterns should be maintained to guarantee the cell immune homeostasis. There is a big amount of evidence that indicate that the transcriptional regulation of NLRs plays an important role for their functioning and correct activation. The first line of evidence shows that expression levels of NLRs increase due to induction of defense when plants are exposed to pathogens or MAMPs (Lai and Eulgem 2018; Chakraborty et al. 2016). In addition, other factors also have been associated with changes in NLR RNA levels, such as tissue differential expression (Munch et al. 2017), circadian rhythm (Bhardwaj et al. 2011; Wang et al. 2011), and phenotype (Rachana et al. 2016). On the other hand, it has been shown that dysregulation of NLRs affects plant growth and yield through the induction of autoimmunity (Borrelli et al. 2018). This has been shown by associating activation of defense signaling with appropriate NLR protein levels: high NLR expression levels and mutations lead to plant developmental disorders and cell death; also, hybrid genetic interaction between NLRs induce autoimmune reactions such as spontaneous hypersensitive response (Lai and Eulgem 2018).

All the evidence here presented, which exposes the importance of NLR regulation and its regulation through several molecular mechanisms, establishes the need of developing new analysis tools that take the comparative genomic research that have been done so far to another level. This proposal looks to design, evaluate and validate a bioinformatic pipeline that integrates RNASeq analysis from different species, ortholog search and genomic features mining to identify key NLR and NLR pairs in plant immune gene repertoire. Given the importance in plant defense and complexity of NLR evolution in plants, this family of proteins has become a priority topic of study in plant pathology, and at the same time, has imposed a big challenge for researchers in understanding ETI response.

With the current knowledge in NLR biology that has been generated using different bioinformatic tools and molecular techniques, we hypothesize that expression data and motif mining contain useful information to infer and prioritize NLR and NLR pairs. We will present bioinformatic tools to predict NLRs, NLR pair proteins and integrate ortholog search and RNASeq data to rank candidates through the inference of expression patterns.

Current needs for integration of NLR prediction and expression patterns

NLRs constitute one of the largest and more diverse gene families in plant immunity. They are central keys for ETI activation and their coevolution with effectors drive a big part of the resistance mechanisms in plants. Their characterization is a research priority for understanding the genetic and molecular mechanisms of plant disease resistance. Understanding better NLR functioning is of outstanding importance in plant breeding to improve crop resistance to the most devastating pathogens. Despite of the large body of literature that has accumulated showing NLR architecture and evolution, researchers have not reached the required resolution to narrow down the hundreds of candidates for functional validation.

During the last decade, several regulation mechanisms of NLR expression have been described, at both post-transcriptional and post-translational level. They involve cis-regulatory elements and transcription factors (TFs), alternative splicing, nonsense-mediated RNA decay (NMD), small RNAs, chromatin-associated, ubiquitination, among others. In order to have a more complete picture of bioinformatic predictions of NLRs based on expression data, it is necessary to start integrating these mechanisms in the pipelines, under the premise that the tighter the regulation, the more important the receptor is in triggering the immune response. For the NLR gene family regulation, some associations between those elements have been identified: 1) It has been shown how NLR genes have overrepresentation of conserved cis-regulatory elements which have been associated with different stimuli including biotic stress, wounding, heat shock and water stress; 2) there are motifs which are conserved in monocots and dicots, and there are also plant-specific motifs as result of genetic diversification; 3) the motif architecture can be associated with gene expression patterns; 4) NLR pairs share common promoters since they are genomic neighbors in inverse orientations, therefore this suggest they can be co-regulated; 5) Alternative splicing acts as a driver for NLR diversity and amplification of resistance-gene variation; 6) temporary alleviation of NMD occurs following a pathogen attack; 7) miRNAs are found to target highly duplicated NLRs (Gandhimani ramkumar, maganti s. madhav, akshaya K. Biswal, s.J.s. rama devi, Kannabiran sakthivel, madhan K. mohan, B. umakanth, satendra K. mangrauthia 2014; Borrelli et al. 2018; Baggs, Dagdas, and Krasileva 2017; Lai and Eulgem 2018).

Recent studies have described the molecular mechanisms that intend to regulate NLR expression at a fine level, having a pivotal role in resistance to biotic stresses. This coincides with the observation that constitutive levels of NLR transcripts are found very narrowly basal states. In addition, when defense is induced, there is NLR differential expression is observed (either full transcripts of specific isoforms). We still are far from understanding the how regulation of NLR activity modulates ETI, for which we require integrative approaches that allow us to use the available expression and genomic data. Deep understanding of these mechanisms will open perspectives for crop improvement, since it will allow us to use key regulatory factors of plant resistance into breeding targets that can be modulated to obtain durable defense response.

Generating a reliable bioinformatic pipeline to predict NLR proteins and NLR pairs by integrating them with an ortholog database of expression data.

Multiple genome-wide comparative analyses of NLRs have been proposed to study their diversity and evolution. These comprise different bioinformatic methodologies, which have given rise to predictions in different species. The number of predictions vary according to the specific pipeline, which increases the variability not only due to biological evidence but to the methods. These approaches have been defined more precisely in recent years, as scientists have advanced in generating better genome resources across several species. In general, the methodologies include a motif prediction tool as Pfam (Bateman et al. 2002) or InterProScan (P. Jones et al. 2014), then, a sequence search based on BLASTP, TBLASTN (Boratyn et al. 2012) or HMMER (Wheeler and Eddy 2013) is used to mine genomes and identify orthologs/paralogs. To compare the obtained sequences there is also a set of choices that include Multiple Expectation Maximization for Motif Elicitation (MEME) and the Motif Alignment and Search Tool (MAST) system, both available in the MEME suite (Bailey et al. 2009). Subsequent phylogenetic and comparative analysis are performed depending on the biological question. In addition, some pipelines combine some of the tools already mentioned, such as the NLR parser (Steuernagel et al. 2015) and RGAugury (P. Li et al. 2016).

In addition to the identification of NLR sequences, many studies have collected RNASeq data in different pathosystems to characterize differential expression of NLR genes under different conditions. Pipelines for RNASeq profiling also have a lot of variations, providing with different tools to map (HISAT, Star), quantify (RSEM, HISAT, Salmon), normalize and compare expression data (EdgeR, DESeq2) (Kim, Langmead, and Salzberg 2015; B. Li and Dewey 2011; Patro et al. 2017; Robinson, McCarthy, and Smyth 2010; Love, Huber, and Anders 2014; Dobin et al. 2013). We want to integrate these two types of pipelines to get a more comprehensive dataset for selection of NLR candidates for validation. The idea behind it is to use datasets across different species that provide us with

more biological evidence to prioritize NLR candidates and to identify potential genes whose expression is correlated (NLR pairs).

The available expression and genomic data can be integrated in a new bioinformatic pipeline that maximizes the amount of biological information for the identification of NLRs and NLR pairs, under the assumption that the expression patterns should be significantly correlated across related species. To establish the different bioinformatic analyses required to test this hypothesis we define a series of input datasets: 1) genomic data from the species of interest and related organisms, which can be provided by the user. Some sources for such data can be downloaded from different databases as Ensembl (Zerbino et al. 2018), GrainGenes ("GrainGenes Webserver," n.d.), NCBI (Benson et al. 2013), TAIR (Berardini et al. 2015), Phytozome (Goodstein et al. 2012). The required files consist in sequence assemblies and proteome predictions in fasta format and annotation files in gtf or gff3. 2) In case the user has a curated list of NLRs, it is possible to provide with the file with the corresponding annotation. 3) expression datasets: RNASeq data for every species provided in 1) and metadata information about the experiment in a provided format (it should contain conditions, time course, mutant gene ids, etc).

Bioinformatic tools predict the NLR proteins using a TBLASTN search with query as the NB-ARC domain (Pfam: PF00931) and the target genome of the species of interest. This should be repeated for all the input genomes, to give reliable comparisons that require testing and optimization of a common set of tools and parameters. Predicted NLR proteins from each species are analyzed using Pfam domain identification pipeline on the run_pfam.pl script. The resulting predictions are parsed using NLR parser. Only highest scoring non-overlapping domains will be retained for each protein. To classify these NBS-encoding genes, all candidate genes should be evaluated to further verify the encoded domains (TIR, CC, NBS, or LRR motifs) using the Pfam database and SMART protein motif analyses.

To process the expression data, every experiment should be analyzed independently. Using the NLRs candidate sequences as reference, the reads could be quality trimmed using Trimmomatic (Bolger, Lohse, and Usadel 2014), mapped and quantified using RSEM and Star software. FPKM normalized counts are used for calculating a Spearman pairwise correlation matrix for each experiment. A permutation test represents an option to find those pair of genes that have an expression correlation higher than expected by chance. Those genes will constitute an initial list of candidates for NLR and NLR pairs.

To make an extensive search and support the analysis using information from different species, candidates can be compared across a set of species of interest with an ortholog search, using InParanoid8 software (Sonnhammer and Östlund 2015), keeping the groups that have a confidence value of 1. Those ortholog groups are used to calculate the

number of times they are significant in the expression correlation permutation test compared with the non-significant group. This is done by testing the significance of co-occurrence of orthologs by hypergeometric Fisher's exact test. If two pairs of orthologs are overrepresented in the significant correlated expression group, the candidates will be prioritized.

Once the groups are defined, the promoters of such genes could be inferred by looking for common cis-regulatory elements: a position weight matrix (PWM) for experimentally validated Arabidopsis and rice TF-CRE pairs can be downloaded from Plant TFDB 4.0 (Jin et al. 2017). MEME suite is used to process it, PWMs are used to match highly similar sequences in the promoter sets using FIMO to calculate a log-likelihood score and q-value for each hit. Then an enrichment score and FDR adjusted p-value is calculated using a Fisher exact test to identify overrepresented motifs relative to random sets of promoter sequences selected at random from the genome. Finally, other type of evidence can be used to rank the candidates, such as genomic location, domain description, orientation and sequence similarity, which in case of NLR pair prediction will help to identify homo and hetero dimers. The pipeline will be tested using the Barley genome and transcriptome resources.

Methods for validating immune-active NLR genes via high-throughput phenotyping and functional assays

The bioinformatic analyses here presented enable the selection of the most significant NLR and NLR pair candidates and predict conserved regulatory elements of disease resistance. Experimental methods to validate the candidates may include rapid transient assays since creation of stable knock-out or over-expression plants is a costly and lengthy process, taking up to 2 years from plasmid constructs to increase of homozygous seed. The available transient options include particle-bombardment-based single-cell overexpression (OEx) (Halterman and Wise 2004) and transient- or host-induced single-cell silencing (TIGS/HIGS) (Hu, Meng, and Wise 2009). Likewise, viral-based assays include virus-induced-gene-silencing (VIGS), microRNA overexpression (MOX), and gene overexpression (VOX). Using these assays, researchers can either inhibit or overexpress a desired NLR or NLR pair and evaluate phenotypic outcomes. The advantage of this method is that one can visualize and digitally document each group of seedlings for quantitative comparison of different treatments. The phenotyped seedlings can be used for nucleic acid isolation for qRT-PCR quantification, thus correlating genotype to phenotype.

Validation of the top ranked candidates (i.e. those that have evidence from all the evaluated features) can be established with a particle bombardment protocol. For each candidate, two non-overlapping cDNA fragments per candidate gene are generally used in order to cross-reference results. qRT-PCR primers are designed independently of the two RNAi fragments to verify that mutant phenotypes are associated with silencing of the target

gene, and to check for off-target effects. Recombinant virions will be used to mechanically infect seedlings of the appropriate genotype with at least ten seedlings per treatment [Mock, empty vector, and gene insert]. After silencing, plants are inoculated with the pathogen of interest and reported in each of the expression data studies whose correlation data was used to make the predictions and phenotypes assessed. For the NLR pair candidates each gene should be silenced individually and both to measure differences.

For those candidates that have an immune-phenotype, methods to dissect the regulation mechanism can be applied by using the predicted cis-regulatory elements. Within the set of promoters for each validated NLR, enriched cis-regulatory elements are taken modelled by composition, orientation, and proximity. Both probabilistic and discriminative models could be employed to detect common regulatory architectures within promoter regions of co-regulated NLR and NLR pairs. TFs predicted to target identified elements can be investigated individually and in combination: direct *in vitro* binding to the DNA element can be measured via electrophoretic mobility shift assays (EMSA). TF proteins are expressed and purified from tobacco. TFs are incubated with a synthesized biotinylated oligonucleotide sequence containing tandem copies of the putative cis-regulatory element and subjected to electrophoretic separation and western blotting using a streptavidin-horseradish peroxidase (HRP) conjugate. As an alternative to EMSA, TF-CRE interactions can be confirmed using enhanced yeast one-hybrid (eY1H) to assay protein-DNA interactions using established protocols (Gaudinier et al. 2017).

Interaction validation *in planta* could be performed by using protoplast chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP) assays. Protoplasts will be transfected with epitope-tagged TF expression constructs using PEG-mediated transformation. For ChIP, transfected protoplasts are treated with formaldehyde to cross-link TF-DNA interactions, chromatin sheared using sonication, and the TF is immunoprecipitated using the appropriate antibody. Immunoprecipitates are washed, reverse cross-linked, and DNA purified and quantified using quantitative PCR. Promoter activation or repression can be confirmed in protoplasts using transient co-expression of the TF and the cis-regulatory element-containing promoter region fused to a firefly luciferase reporter. Protoplasts are co-transfected with TF expression and promoter:luciferase reporter constructs. Luciferase expression is measured by a quantitative luminescence assay using a mutated motif promoter sequence as a control. To evaluate the effect of the genomic location in the expression of NLR and NLR pairs, we propose a bidirectional-Luciferase reporter assay: by mimicking their promoter architecture, modifying the promoter distance (0-10 Kbp) between the firefly and renilla luciferase genes, which are allocated in a bicistronic promoter, and check for changes in the expression levels. By silencing individual or related TFs using a viral system and infecting plants, using RNASeq, the expression of the NLR and NLR pairs can be monitored. This would enable the validation of the predictions and allow the researcher to identify more genes that represent each expression cluster.

Together, these strategies are expected to validate the NLR predictions. Using this integrative approach allows the confirmation of the *in silico* predictions by measuring the candidate's immune phenotype of the silencing and overexpression, and their regulation by transcription factors. Results will generate a view of plant immunity and we expect many of these results to be broadly applicable to other multiple NLR systems, opening possibilities of application in crop improvement. For the NLR and NLR pair validated candidates, we expect these methods to offer a deeper understanding of the regulatory mechanisms that control their expression, and the effects of misregulation of every pair, offering more insights about their origin and evolution. With these new set of pairs we can test their domain architecture and dependency, information that we can contrast with previous studies that assure their contain non-conserved domains (Cesari et al. 2014).

Conclusions

NLR expression can be regulated by a set of interesting molecular mechanisms, and this project is looking to evaluate one of them in depth (cis-regulatory elements and transcription factors). Once this general mechanism is better understood, other different processes could be evaluated and how they coalesce to get a tight NLR regulation. These include regulation by small RNAs, non-sense mediated decay, alternative splicing, and chromatin-associated. Furthermore, once the immune relevance of the NLR candidate is demonstrated it would be necessary to characterize them better in terms of their interactions with hosts proteins and pathogen effectors, which can be measured using different methods (De Las Rivas and Fontanillo 2010). For NLR pairs there is a prevailing question about the function of their non-conserved domains: experimental observations of their high diversity suggest that they do not play a critical role in signaling or regulation within the pair (Cesari et al. 2014). Therefore, characterization of the function of such domains is a key aim for understanding these proteins.

The development of novel approaches that integrates RNASeq analysis across species, ortholog identification, and genomic feature mining represents a significant advancement in comparative genomic research of NLRs. By enabling the systematic discovery of key NLRs and NLR pairs within plant immune repertoires. Here we presented tools that will provide a robust framework for understanding the genetic basis of disease resistance. Beyond its methodological contribution, the deeper insights into NLR regulation mechanisms will have broad implications for agriculture, as they open new avenues for crop improvement through the identification of regulatory factors that can be harnessed as breeding targets. Ultimately, this work lays the foundation for durable defense responses in plants, strengthening both scientific knowledge and practical strategies for sustainable crop production.

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